

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Evaluation of Class Observations on the Teaching Performance of the School of Education Instructors: Their Best Teaching Practices

Sol G. Simbulan, Ph.D.

School of Education, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon

Correspondence to: solsimbulan@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Highlighted in this study is the evaluation of the classroom instructional performance of the college instructors in the School of Education (SED) at San Isidro College during the 1st semester of the AY 2019-2020. The dean of the SED observed nine college instructors teaching in their respective disciplines using the class observation evaluation form. Findings revealed that the college instructors were rated as excellent in the three major component *on teacher as a professional, teacher effectiveness and classroom environment*. From the class observation, the college instructors demonstrated their particular teaching strategies, types of questions raised, classroom interaction, and best teaching practices.

Key words: *Evaluation, Class Observation on Instruction, Teaching Practices*

INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of class observations done to teachers by the school administrators plays a significant role in teaching and learning. It helps teachers and learners enrich their teaching performance and learning abilities. It is a continuous process and a periodic exercise. It serves as an in-built monitor within the course to review the progress in learning from time to time. It also provides valuable feedback on what transpired in the classroom and on how teachers and students manage to traverse the educational landscape (Education, 2021).

Classroom observation and teacher evaluation are standardized processes of rating and assessing the teaching effectiveness of educators. Teacher's performance evaluations help promote a better learning experience for students and foster their personal and professional growth (iAuditor, 2021). The classroom observation as an evaluation for teacher's teaching performance can be an opportunity for genuine professional learning. It could offer opportunity for teachers to reflect on their own teaching practices and to promote better learning for students.

Charlotte Danielson, a curriculum director and administrator, believes that teacher evaluation should be student-focused or linked to classroom performance rather than solely observing the teacher. Traditionally, in the elementary or secondary classrooms, teacher evaluation is conducted by a principal, department head, or teacher evaluator who observes how a teacher handles a class with the help of checklists. The same is true to observing classes in the college level. The evaluation could consider other factors like assessments, lesson plans, daily records, class attendance and student outputs. In addition to classroom management, teaching strategies, classroom interactions, active participation, questioning techniques and lesson engagement, both the students and instructors are also given importance when evaluating teaching performance (CRLT, 2019).

The principal, supervisor, instructional head, chairperson, dean or fellow teacher could either conduct a formal or informal classroom observation of teaching while it is taking place in a classroom or other learning environment. These classroom observations are often used to provide teachers with constructive critical feedback aimed at improving

their classroom management and instructional techniques. School administrators regularly observe teachers for the semester-end or year-end evaluation of performance. These reports of performance are usually needed for year-end reports, promotion, and increase in salaries and bonuses.

Classroom observations may be conducted for shorter or longer periods of time—from a few minutes to a full class period or school day. There is a wide variety of classroom observation methods that could be utilized as tools for evaluation. Generally, observation tools or instruments use common templates or guidelines that describe what observers should be looking for or what the observed teacher would like to be given feedback on.

In the School of Education (SED) at San Isidro College, the dean usually conducts semestral class observations as a way of monitoring teaching performance and best practices. There is a homegrown evaluation form for classroom instruction at the SED office. There are 3 broad components used for evaluation which include the teacher as a professional, teacher effectiveness, and class environment.

This study assessed class observation as a source of information on the best teaching practices of observed SED instructors during the 1st semester of academic year 2019-2020, with the rationale that college teachers are very creative in their teaching craft and therefore could radiate their best teaching practices in terms of teaching strategies, questioning techniques, and classroom interaction.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study works on the premise that classroom observation provides a meaningful teacher evaluation of instruction. This involves an accurate appraisal of the effectiveness of teaching, its strengths and areas

for development, followed by feedback, coaching, support and opportunities for professional development (OECD, 2009). The classroom observation of the SED faculty in their instruction is evaluated using the San Isidro College evaluation guide. This includes 3 major components on *teacher as a professional*, on *teacher effectiveness*, and on *classroom environment*. From the observation of teacher's instruction, evaluation on teaching strategies, types of questions raised, classroom interaction and best practices in teaching are also highlighted. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual schema of the study.

The *teacher as a professional* means conducting oneself according to the highest standards, giving the best effort inside and outside the classroom, and building relationships based on mutual respect It means looking and acting like one. Professionals keep their work up to date and plan ahead. True professionals, in any field, embrace the corporate identity and values, and model these for the clients. In the case of a teacher, it means being a "team player" with fellow teachers and the school administration, and projecting this shared focus to the students. True professionals behave well in public and are someone who others can respect no matter the situation. They prepare thoroughly for each day of teaching. They check their plans the evening before and get ready for the following day. Professional teachers plan thoroughly for every lesson and class. They stick to their work program and assessment schedule. This ensures that syllabus content is covered, and also the necessary skills for their students' longer-term success in their specific subject or learning area. A professional teacher's workday does not end with the school bell at the end of the day, and it always starts before the morning bell the next day. A professional teacher understands the need to start the day well, every day (Listman, 2020).

Generally, *teacher effectiveness* show that teachers plan carefully, use appropriate materials,

communicate goals to students, maintain a brisk pace, assess student work regularly, and use a variety of teaching strategies. They use class time well and have coherent strategies for instruction. They hold the expectations that their students can learn and believe that they have a large responsibility to help (Cohen et al., 2003). Effective instruction for an individual lesson includes daily review, statement of objective, teacher presentation, guided practice, independent practice, and evaluation of learning objectives (Andrews, 2004)

The teacher plays an important role in the classroom when it comes to the *teaching environment*. If a teacher prepares a warm, happy environment, students are more likely to be happy. An environment set by the teacher can either have positive or negative effect in student's learning. Teachers are responsible for the social behaviors of the students in their classrooms and this reflects teacher's action and the environment that is set (MOE, 2015).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study evaluated and analyzed the class observation results of the SED college instructors at San Isidro College during the first semester of AY 2019-2020. It answered the questions on:

1. What is the evaluation of the SED college instructors' teaching performance based on the classroom observation considering:
 - 1.1 teacher as a professional;
 - 1.2 teacher effectiveness; and
 - 1.3 classroom environment?
2. What is the percentage on the type of questions raised by the SED college instructors in their class?
3. What is the percentage of classroom interaction recorded during the class observation?
4. What are the comments on the teaching performance of the college instructors during the class observation?
5. What are the best practices of the SED college instructors in the conduct of their classes during the class observation?

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study utilized the descriptive research design employing qualitative analysis based from the result

of actual class observations done to nine (48%) college instructors teaching the different fields of specializations. The School of Education at San Isidro College served as the research locale where the classroom observations occurred.

San Isidro College is dubbed as the only Catholic Institution of Higher learning located at Impalambong Malaybalay City. It was founded by Jesuit Missionaries in July 1949 and is duly accredited by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd). It is also a member of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP) and the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS). Its motto *Ora et Labora* which means *prayer and work* is the famous adage of San Isidro Labrador the patron saint of Malaybalay City. From its humble beginnings, the school continues to provide quality Catholic Education where students adhere to its vision, mission and core values.

During the first semester of the academic year 2019-2020, there were a total of nineteen faculty members, six of whom have full-time status and the rest have part-time status, although most of these part-timers are full-time teachers in the elementary or senior high of the Integrated Basic Education group. The SED enrolment for college students totaled to 201 warm bodies spread across the different year levels and programs in their major fields.

The major instrument used for the classroom observation is a survey instrument form containing 3 major components, namely: *the teacher as a professional* with five statements elucidating the mastery of the teacher in showing confidence and positivity; in articulating clearly with voice and gestures; in communicating both English and Filipino effectively; in mastery of the subject matter; and in good time management. The second component is on *teacher effectiveness* with nine statements mostly highlighting the objectives of the lesson; the subject matter; the instructional materials used, the strategies use; the class activities; the questioning techniques; and the attainment of the objectives. The third component is on *class environment* with four statements underscoring students' engagement of the lesson, participation, rapport and class management. There is also a space for narrative comments, suggestions and recommendations for the observed teacher to provide for qualitative inputs on what were

observed. A 5-point Likert scale evaluates the class observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of the SED Instructors under the three major components

Table 1 shows the evaluation of the SED college instructors during their class observation based on the classroom observation evaluation guide. Generally,

show mastery of the subject matter. They used class time to full advantage.

Under the component on *teacher effectiveness*, the instructors introduce the lesson, objectives and expectations to prepare and motivate the class. They relate subject matter to previous concepts/topics and to other fields or current events. They present new materials in organized form. They provide critical thinking and creativity through techniques of

Table 1. Evaluation of the SED Instructors during their class observation under the three major components

Indicator	T-1	T-2	T-3	T-4	T-5	T-6	T-7	T-8	T-9	Total	QD	
1 Teacher as a professional	4.00	5.00	4.80	4.80	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.80	4.89	Excellent	
2 Teacher Effectiveness	3.78	4.78	4.44	4.44	4.67	4.78	4.67	4.78	4.56	4.54	Excellent	
3 The class environment	4.00	5.00	4.50	4.75	4.75	5.00	4.75	5.00	4.50	4.69	Excellent	
Total	3.92	4.93	4.58	4.66	4.81	4.93	4.81	4.93	4.62	4.71	Excellent	
Legend:	5	4.20-5.00 Excellent (E)					2	1.80-2.59 Fair (F)				
	4	3.40-3.19 Very Good (VG)					1	1.00-1.79 Poor (P)				
	3	2.60-3.39 Good (G)					T-1 to 9 Teachers Observed					

the evaluation based from the components showed a rating of 4.71 indicating that the SED instructors demonstrated an *excellent* performance in their teaching practice. It is in the component on the *teacher as professional* where the rating was very high, followed by the *class environment*, then *teacher effectiveness*. All the components have an *excellent* rating, indicating that the SED instructors showed their best teaching practice.

Under the component on *teacher as a professional*, the instructors showed confidence and positive attitude in their teaching. They articulate clearly, use voice and gestures to advantage. They communicate in English/Filipino effectively. They

questioning and discussion. They use appropriate teaching aids, AV, references, and board work. Their class activities lead to the achievement of lesson objectives. They respond to student’s questions, responses, comments, and opinions effectively. They provide activities for students to know that learning is taking place. There are evidences that lesson objectives have been attained.

In the third component on the *class environment*, the students’ attention and interest are sustained throughout the lesson. The class participated through answers, questions, explanations, citations, examples, statistics/data, etc. There is rapport between the teacher and students that enhances the learning

Table 2. Evaluation of the SED instructors on the percentage of the types of questions they raised during their class as observed

Questions Raised	T-1	T-2	T-3	T-4	T-5	T-6	T-7	T-8	T-9	Total
<i>Lower-order thinking skills</i>										
1 • Knowledge	90%	76%	100%	81%	48%	96%	92%	NA	100%	85.37%
• Comprehension										
• Application										
<i>Higher-order thinking skills</i>										
2 • Analysis	10%	24%	0%	19%	42%	4%	8%	NA	0%	14.63%
• Synthesis										
• Evaluation										

process. Class management promotes wholesome and effective learning atmosphere.

Evaluation of the SED Instructors on the percentage of the types of questions they raised

Table 2 reflects the percentage on the types of questions raised by the SED instructors during the class observation. Questions are a teacher's incredible tool to keep a lesson active, alive and flowing. These accentuate the understanding of concepts as well as clarify misconceptions that opens-up discussions and allow students to have a deeper understanding of the topic (Fulbrook, 2019). Often teachers raised questions in their classes yet many of these are developing the lower-order thinking skills. It is evident that the SED instructors raised 85.37% lower-order category questions on knowledge, comprehension and application, and only 14.63% higher-order category on analysis, synthesis, and evaluation.

The lower order category questions on knowledge or remembering refer to asking questions on identification and recall of information – knowledge of events, places, dates and major ideas. Comprehension or understanding refers to asking questions about the organization and selection of facts and ideas – understanding information, grasping meaning, translating knowledge into a new context, order, group and infer causes. Application refers to asking questions about the facts, rules and principles: use information, methods concepts and theories in new situations (Knaack, 2001).

Effective ways of asking questions need to be prepared by teachers so that their questions would not cluster on the lower order categories alone. There should also be higher-order category questions on analysis, synthesis and evaluation (Simbulan, 1993). Analysis refers to asking questions about the subdivision of a whole into component parts: seeing patterns, recognition of hidden meanings, and identification of components. Evaluation refers to asking questions about the subdivision of a whole into component parts: seeing patterns, recognition of hidden meanings, and identification of components. Synthesis refers to asking questions about the combination of ideas to form a new whole: using old ideas to create new ones, generalize from given facts, relate knowledge from several areas and predict/draw conclusions (Knaack, 2001).

The desirability to prepare questions with a particular group of students in mind was postulated by Cohen and Manion (1990). It is particularly useful when framing questions as a part of class preparation to distinguish broad categories of questions, that is, those that test knowledge and those that create knowledge. The former involves the lower-order thinking skills questions while the later are the higher-order thinking skills questions

There are studies revealing that many of the teachers' questions fall into the recall category which is of the lower-order bracket and that the higher-order categories were rarely used. The same findings were stated by Carin (1970) where surveys indicated that over 90% of all the questions raised by teachers were merely for reproducing what was just read, heard or seen, Similarly Anderson and Burns (1989) indicated that questions asked during classroom discussions were merely of the lower-order category calling for brief and short responses.

The findings were reinforced by Simbulan (1993) stating that students from all grade and year levels in the elementary, secondary, and tertiary levels predominantly raised lower-order category questions. Very likely, the ripple effect of teachers asking lower-order questions influence their students who later on will become teachers and will follow the styles of their previous teachers. The implication here is that when teachers merely gave lower-order questions they are merely developing their lower order thinking skills.

Evaluation on classroom interaction of the SED instructors and their students

The pioneering study of Ned Flanders on classroom analysis described the interaction between teachers and students both in the verbal and non-verbal communication (Amidon & Hough, 1968). Flanders listed 10 categories in the FIAS (Flanders Interaction Analysis System), divided into 4 subdivisions, namely: teacher indirect verbal behavior, teacher direct verbal behavior, student verbal behavior, and silence or nonfunctional verbal

Table 3. Evaluation of the SED instructors on the percentage of Classroom Interaction in the conduct of their class during the class observation

Class Interaction	T-1	T-2	T-3	T-4	T-5	T-6	T-7	T-8	T-9	Total	
<i>Teacher Indirect Influence</i>											
1	• Accepts feelings • Praises and encourages • Accepts ideas	6%	12%	9%	4%	4%	12%	0%	16%	2%	7.22%
<i>Teacher Direct Influence</i>											
2	• Asks questions • Lectures • Gives directions • Criticizes	66.58%	34%	54%	63%	35%	69%	89%	71%	52.67%	57.14%
<i>Student's interaction</i>											
3	• Student response • Student initiation	24.56%	54%	37%	30%	42%	19%	17%	13%	36.67%	30.47%
<i>Silence or nonfunctional verbal interaction</i>											
4		2.6%		3%	19%		14%		8.67%	5.25%	

behavior. Table 3 reflects the classroom interaction of the teachers and students during their classes.

As observed the teachers' *direct influence* is very evident with 57.14%. Under this direct influence of the teacher include their asking of questions, giving of lectures, giving of directions and criticizes. This is reciprocated by the students' interaction as shown by their responses and their initiation for verbal communication giving 30.47%.

Comments on the classroom observations of the SED instructors

Matrix 1 shows the excerpts on the general comments as recorded during the class observations. It is noted that all the nine instructors teaching inside their classrooms utilized the lecture method coupled with other strategies, like: lecture-discussion; lecture-discussion-demonstration; lecture with creative techniques using poems, songs, role play; lecture using the ICT; and lecture with reporting. The P.E class however was more on demonstration and execution. The lecture was mostly on giving directions.

The lecture method of teaching is the oldest teaching method applied in schools. This teaching method is usually a one-way channel of

communication of information, where the teacher does the verbal communication all the time (SLN, 2019). Teachers generally do the lecture because they can teach a large amount of topic that can cover a single class period to the whole class. However, individual differences of the learners may not be addressed and the active involvement of the students may not be enhanced by mere listening to the lecture. Hence, the teachers in the School of Education did not exclusively use the lecture method but combine other strategies and techniques that they considered most appropriate for their presentation.

As to the type of questions that they raised, all of them prevalently used the lower-order types of questions. This could have been reinforced if they have prepared the questions to be raised in their lesson guide to include higher order questions. At this level, teachers need to prepare the learners for higher-order thinking skills,

Classroom communication is a vital component in the instructional and learning process in the school environment. The quality and quantity of teacher-student interaction is a critical dimension of effective classroom teaching. The development of the original system of interaction analysis of Ned Flanders made possible significant insights into the analysis and improvement of instruction. Flanders'

Matrix 1. Excerpts of the general comments on the evaluation of the SED instructors during their class observations	
Teacher Observed	General Comments on the class observation of the SED instructors
T-1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is a review lesson for the Prelims exam, hence the teaching strategy used is more of lecture-discussion (question & answer) Teacher demonstrates an aura of confidence, moving about while lecturing and asking questions. Most of the questions raised were of the knowledge and comprehension level, and these were usually of the cloze type of questioning wherein the teacher allowed the students to complete the statement that he gave. There is good rapport between the teacher and students When the teacher sketched the cube on the board, the students watched intently, hence it is good if there are illustrations done. This shows that basically, the students are more of visual learners. <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-discussion</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 59% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Teacher asks questions-35%</i></p>
T-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prayers and class routines were done. The strategies used in this class on <i>caregiving</i> is a combination of the lecture-discussion-demonstration. The lecture is either done by the teacher and the students who did the reporting. The students did the report by groups previously assigned by the teacher, and they are prepared with their reports. Actual mannequin was used in the demonstration on caregiving, e.g. changing of diapers, and maintaining cleanliness of the patient. Learning-by-doing is manifested. The teacher reinforced the report of the students with her inputs and additional lecture There are evidences of good classroom management <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-discussion-demonstration</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 43% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Student-Talk Response-31%</i></p>
T-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher is smiling. She greeted her class convivially, and animation prayer was done by the students. She called the roll and gave instructions of the activity that they will have for the day. Students were asked to present the output of their interview with couples and family in relation to their marriage/married life. These were illustrated in bond paper, and the students demonstrated their report through a song, a poem, dramatization and role play. <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture- with creative techniques from Students (poem, song, role play)</i> <i>Questions raised: Comprehension level 43% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Student Talk Initiation-29%</i></p>
T-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher asked a student to lead the prayer She depicts a pleasant personality and is smiling at her class. She reviewed the previous lesson, then proceeded with the lecture proper on the "Nature of Marriage" The outline of the lesson for the day was provided to the students for them to follow what is being lectured. The strategy used was more of a lecture method with some questions interlaced during the process. There were instances where the statements ended with a question, hence the strategy was more on lecture-discussion The topic on "marriage" was interesting hence the students were very attentive. Class management is evident. Teacher gives immediate evaluation after the lesson <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-discussion</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 62% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Teacher asks questions-31%</i></p>

<p>T-5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prayer in Filipino was recited by the students • Teacher is very articulate in her presentation and showed evidences of well-preparedness. • Class management was good despite the long duration of the class (3-hour period). There were only 13 students and she grouped them into 4 groups. • Prepared activities for the different language skills – listening, speaking, reading, and writing, were done. • The students were empowered to do the activities through conversation, dialogs, role playing. • Higher-order questions were raised allowing the students to think about their responses. • There were instances where the teacher tried to inject how the learning of the students could be embedded in the MV of the school, but this was not pursued relentlessly. This is a good start for integrating the MV of the school <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-with student creative techniques</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 47% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Student Talk Initiation-22%</i></p>
<p>T-6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prayers were said. • The teacher is alive and vibrant contaminating the students with enthusiasm and stamina. This is good because the class schedule is at 1PM where students are prone to be sleepy. • Teacher praises and encourages the students, motivating them with visual aids like pictures, emoticons, and the presentation of the lessons through the PowerPoint. • The strategy is a combination of the lecture-discussion-demonstration with the integration of the new technology. • The lecture was well-prepared and the teacher shows promise of being a good lecturer/speaker during SW as she is very emphatic, alive and clear in her presentation. • The lecture was rich, substantial and loaded with information such that the students seemed to be overwhelmed with the contents presented, that they were silent when asked if they are convinced to do research. • While the teacher’s voice is loud and clear, maybe there is a need to modulate this because there is a danger that she will strain her throat. <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-with Integration of New Technology</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 78% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Teacher gives lecture-37%</i></p>
<p>T-7</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prayers were recited. • Teacher demonstrated a pleasant personality. • The lecture-discussion-demonstration was utilized as her strategy in presenting the lesson. • The topic on <i>Measures of Central Tendency</i> – specifically the <i>Median</i> was presented using the PowerPoint, as well as, the extensive use of the blackboard • The teacher is solicitous as to whether the students understood the lecture-demonstration by asking questions. Her tone of voice seems to constantly ask a question. • Individual students were asked, however, they prefer to answer in chorus, so the teacher asked them to read what were written in her PPT and they read in chorus. [Choral reading is a technique that allow students to participate in the class recitation, however, we could limit its use if this is not a reading class.] • Activity sheets were given for the students to work in groups. These are mostly on finding the median. • While the students were working in their group activity, the teacher moves around to check on their work. This is a good way to monitor students’ involvement and participation. <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-discussion-demonstration</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 78% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Teacher gives lectures-31%</i></p>
<p>T-8</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is a PE class (on dances) hence the students are in the gym. • Prayers were said • The teacher is active, alive, vibrant and very energetic exemplifying a pleasant personality. • She is organized with her records and class activities; prepared her class materials systematically labeling them accordingly. • Despite the nature of the subject which is outdoor, the teacher has a good command of her class, demonstrating good outdoor class management.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actual performance of the dance steps was done; and the students performed as instructed. • Teacher is very graceful and exhibited a good model for the students in all the steps taught • Individual coaching was also done to check on students' performance <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Demonstration-Execution</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level (LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Teacher gives direction-60%</i></p>
T-9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher started her class with a student leading the prayer. • The usual class routines were done, e.g. checking of attendance, etc. • Teacher shows confidence in her teaching. She introduced the topic/s for the day, then proceeded by asking the assigned students to do the reporting. • Student reporting is good because this could force the students to do research, study their report and present their report, however, it is best if they are encouraged/coached to present their report without merely reading this, because the students who are listening will get bored. Besides, there were limited discussions and explanations on what were read. • The reading of the PowerPoint reports was done in succession and after the 3rd reporter, the teacher re-enforced what were reported. • She gave additional information about the topics reported by the students. • A video presentation was shown by the students on the TPACK, to reinforce the report done earlier. This is better because it made the lesson clearer as this was in animation. • At the end of the topics and reports, the teacher asked a student to recapitulate on what they have learned from the lessons. <p><i>Teaching Strategy Used: Lecture-with students reporting</i> <i>Questions raised: Knowledge level 90% -(LOTS)</i> <i>Interaction: Student Talk Response--37%</i></p>

Matrix 2. Identified Best Practices of the SED instructors during the class observation & evaluation	
<i>Teacher Observed/</i>	<i>Best teaching practices of the SED instructors during the class observation & evaluation</i>
T-1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher demonstrates confidence and is calm in his teaching approach; • There is good rapport between teacher and students
T-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a good participation and involvement of the students in their learning • Actual demonstration is a good preparation for real-life practice • Teacher is a facilitator of learning
T-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is good participation of students through the assigned interview; presentation of the interview in varied medium • Actual/real-life experiences were given
T-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher is an active lecturer, smiling and accommodating to students' questions • Evaluation after the lecture facilitates immediate feedback on students' learning
T-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students' involvement and participation in the activities through dialogs, role play, question and answer, and demonstrating their skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing (in Filipino) • Teacher is a facilitator of learning • Varied activities are presented
T-6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher's enthusiasm and passion to teach • Preparation of Instructional Materials to sustain the interest for the lesson • Well-prepared lecture
T-7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were activities for the students to work on • Monitoring from the teacher on students' work was done • Teacher was solicitous on students' understanding of the lesson
T-8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good modeling from the teacher on the dance steps • Individual coaching and mentoring of the students
T-9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of video presentation • Recapitulation on what was learned

interaction analysis system (FIAS) is an observational tool used to classify the verbal behavior of teachers and pupils as they interact in the classroom (Amatari. 2015).

The teacher could have an indirect or direct influence in the component on teacher-talk. Their indirect response include accepts feelings, praises or encourages, and accepts ideas. Their direct influence includes ask questions, lecture, give direction and criticize or justify authority. Student-talk on the other hand includes response and initiation.

The SED classroom interaction showed that five instructors were more *direct* in their influence as they utilized: teacher asks questions, teacher gives lectures, and teacher gives direction. Four instructors showed that they allowed more student-talk response and student-talk initiation. Generally, this is true when the teacher let the students do the reporting using the PowerPoint presentation.

Best Practices demonstrated during the class observations

Matrix 2 listed the best practices of the SED instructors in their class instruction. There are best practices exhibited by the SED instructors during their class demonstration.

On *routine activities* the teachers generally start with a prayer either led by the teacher, but mostly the students were requested to lead. As a Catholic institution this is one best practice because it develops in the student the habit of invoking the guidance and direction of the Divine Providence, building in them good character and enhancing the core values of the school. Another best practice observed is the kind of aura that the teacher presents to the students, where they showed confidence, give smile, enthusiasm, and other positive vibrations. This glowing aura from the teacher could radiate a pleasant mode to start the day's lesson.

Before the presentation of the lesson, one best practice that teacher have is to clearly present the goals and objectives of the day's lesson. They present what are the expected outcomes of the lesson. This is good because the teacher and the students could journey together with the same objective and goal in

mind. It will also serve as their guide as to whether the lesson is in sync with the course objectives and goals. It could allow the students to keep track of their progress in learning.

Under *strategies enacted on the spot*, one best practice is on monitoring students work and activities. Teachers know their students by name and could recognize if they participate in the discussion or activities. The teachers are also ready to coach and mentor the students allowing them to ask questions if they did not understand the lesson. They are solicitous on whether students understand or not. There is good modeling from the teacher when they demonstrate an activity.

On their *lecture presentation*, one best practice is when teachers supplement their lecture with PowerPoint presentation; show visual aids, pictures, video; present with clear voice and gestures, and provide hands-on activities. These could help them to facilitate their teaching and enhance students' active involvement in the lesson.

Finally, at the *end of their class activities* teacher recapitulates the lesson or ask the students to do the recapitulation; give activities for assignment; give a birds-eye view on what they will do next meeting, then end with a closing prayer.

Marzano (2015) cited 13 teaching best practices, where some of these are practiced by the SED instructors like communicating course assignments, rules and procedures; Providing students materials and references to do the assigned tasks; Clearly presenting goals and objectives of the lessons and assignment; Offering encouragement and feedback to the students; Allowing the student to keep track of their progress; Accessibility to the students, either online or face-to-face; Monitoring student work; Knowing the students' name and recognizing them; Allowing the students to progress at their own pace; Providing help to understand and practice new knowledge; Allowing the students to ask questions; Treating all students equally; and Adding external resources to assignment.

CONCLUSIONS

In a nutshell, class observations led to effective monitoring and evaluation of teaching which is central to the continuous improvement of the

effectiveness of teaching in a school. It is essential to know the strengths of teachers and those aspects of their practice which could be further developed. From this perspective, classroom observation becomes a vital step in the drive to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning and raise educational standards (OECD, 2009). Sawchuk (2019) mentioned that teacher evaluation through class observation could review and rate teacher's performance in the actual setting. The class observations conducted to the SED faculty showcased their best teaching practices, their teaching strategies, classroom interaction and questioning techniques. Ideally, the feedback from the observations could help guide teachers in the improvement of their teaching, particularly in their questioning techniques and in the types of questions that they give to their students, as well as in their classroom interaction and teaching strategies. Classroom observation could provide teachers the evaluation that could help them grow as professionals, as expert teachers, and as facilitator of learning in the teaching environment no matter how long they have been in the classroom (TNTP, 2019).

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